

Improving Clinical Management Through Digital Communication: A Mixed-Methods Study on Chat Use Between General Practitioners and Hospital Specialists in Milan, Italy

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Abstract

Introduction: Communication between general practitioners (GPs) and hospital specialists is essential for the efficient management of patients. The use of digital tools such as chat systems facilitates real-time clinical information sharing, reduces wait times for specialist consultations, and enhances interprofessional collaboration.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Garbagnate Hospital and included both quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative data measured the average response times to chat messages between GPs and hospital specialists, categorized by medical specialty. Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews to explore physicians' perceptions of chat use in daily clinical practice. A total of 29 GPs (52% male, 48% female) and 9 hospital specialists (67% male, 33% female) participated in the study.

Results: Over a four-month period, 237 questions were exchanged via the chat system. Gynecology received the highest number of questions (n = 79), while otolaryngology received the fewest (n = 11). The average response time across all specialties was 27 minutes, although substantial variation was observed. GPs perceived digital communication as a valuable tool that improved clinical autonomy and potentially reduced the burden on the healthcare system. However, areas for improvement were identified, particularly regarding GP training to ensure clearer and more

structured requests, and the reorganization of response workflows in specialties with longer response times, such as otolaryngology.

Conclusions: The use of chat systems between GPs and specialists can significantly enhance patient management and interprofessional communication. To maximize these benefits, targeted investments in physician training and workflow optimization within slower-responding specialties are recommended.

Keywords: Digital communication; General practitioners; Hospital specialists; Interprofessional collaboration; Chat systems; Clinical decision-making; Primary care; Response time; Teleconsultation; Workflow optimization.

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INTRODUCTION

General practice is among the most complex and multifaceted disciplines in the healthcare system. Despite this, its complexity and central role are often underappreciated. The general practitioner (GP) serves as the primary point of contact for patients, managing a wide range of conditions, from acute illnesses to chronic diseases requiring long-term monitoring, from preventive care to etiological diagnosis, and even palliative care.

In addition to maintaining a solid foundation of multidisciplinary knowledge, GPs must stay continuously updated on advancements across numerous medical fields and new technologies applied to clinical practice. However, despite their comprehensive training, situations often arise in which GPs encounter complex issues that necessitate immediate specialist support. This need is frequently hindered by long waiting times in the Italian National Health Service (SSN), delaying timely access to specialist care.

In recent years, the use of smartphones and mobile applications in clinical practice has grown exponentially, transforming how healthcare professionals communicate and access information. A review by Lee et al. (2023) found that smartphones are now an essential component of clinical practice, widely used for communication, decision-making support, and medical information consultation among both specialists and GPs [1]. Smartphones allow rapid access to evidence-based resources, improving efficiency and care quality [2].

One of the most frequently used tools for facilitating communication among healthcare professionals is WhatsApp, a messaging platform not specifically designed for medical use. WhatsApp is employed not only for communication between colleagues but also for direct contact with patients [3]. This rapid form of communication has reduced wait times for specialist consultations and improved coordination across different levels of the healthcare system. However, various studies have highlighted challenges related to patient data confidentiality and security when using unregulated tools like WhatsApp [4]. Concerns regarding privacy and the lack of regulatory oversight have been frequently reported in the literature, underscoring the need for stricter institutional policies [5,6].

In addition to communication, smartphones are widely used for clinical decision-making support. Applications such as Medscape and UpToDate provide immediate access to updated, evidence-based information, aiding diagnosis and

therapeutic management [7]. Studies show that most physicians regularly use these apps for pharmacological references and continuous medical education [8,9]. According to Lee et al. [1], the main barriers to smartphone use include limited internet connectivity and insufficient technological support in hospitals [10]. Furthermore, physicians have expressed concerns about the quality and safety of information provided by some medical apps, raising the need for greater regulation and validation [11].

Smartphones are also increasingly used to manage electronic health records and plan medical activities. Tools like Google Calendar and patient monitoring apps have proven useful in improving organization and continuity of care [12,13]. Nevertheless, integration of smartphones into hospital systems remains limited, partly due to a lack of interoperability between mobile devices and hospital infrastructures [14].

One of the main obstacles to care quality is the fragmentation of the care pathway due to inadequate communication among healthcare providers. This fragmentation not only reduces the effectiveness of care but can also create confusion and dissatisfaction for patients [15].

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified interprofessional collaboration (IPC) in both training and clinical practice as a key strategy to address the global healthcare crisis. According to the WHO, IPC helps overcome care fragmentation by promoting a holistic approach that values the specific competencies of each professional. In this context, collaboration between GPs and specialists (e.g., cardiologists, oncologists, psychologists) is essential to ensure a multidisciplinary approach to care [16]. A central tenet of IPC is the daily encounter with professional diversity, fostering mutual recognition and respect for each other's contributions to shared patient care [17,18].

To manage issues spanning multiple specialties, it is essential not only to promote continuous training but also to improve access to specialist resources and encourage interprofessional collaboration between GPs and hospital specialists. Numerous studies have demonstrated that interprofessional collaboration significantly enhances care quality and patient satisfaction. A literature review by Morgan et al. [15] showed that patients receiving coordinated care from multiple professionals report improved continuity, fewer medical errors, and greater overall satisfaction.

IPC also directly impacts patient safety. Poor coordination and communication among healthcare providers are linked to increased medical error risk. Through IPC, this risk can be mitigated by sharing information and expertise to identify and resolve critical issues early. Another benefit of IPC lies in enhancing the work experience of healthcare professionals. Structured collaboration fosters shared responsibility and reduces stress associated with managing complex cases independently, ultimately leading to greater job satisfaction.

To integrate IPC into the healthcare system, it is necessary to invest in training future healthcare professionals. According to the WHO, Interprofessional Education (IPE) is fundamental to preparing physicians, nurses, and other professionals to work together in multidisciplinary teams. IPE aims to create a culture of collaboration where mutual respect and appreciation of others' expertise are core values of medical practice.

In 2021, as part of a GP training program promoted by urology specialists at Garbagnate Hospital, a WhatsApp chat was introduced for professional exchange. Initially created to support trainee doctors, the initiative quickly expanded thanks to its effectiveness and the efforts of the course coordinator, Dr. Marone. Originally limited to urology, the chats soon included general surgery, vascular surgery, cardiology, gynecology, and ENT specialists. Currently, six active chats facilitate continuous interaction between GPs and hospital specialists.

This form of communication has created a virtual clinical community where physicians can consult each other rapidly, receive timely responses, and access qualified specialist opinions, thereby improving patient care. However, despite its many advantages, digital group chats also pose challenges, such as increased workload for specialists and the need for GPs to formulate clear and relevant questions.

Objective

This study aims to analyze the experience of Garbagnate Hospital in using digital chats between GPs and hospital specialists. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate usage frequency, response times, and the perceived impact of these interactions on daily clinical practice. The study also aims to understand GPs' perception of the chats' usefulness in patient management and explore specialists' views on feasibility and benefits of digital collaboration.

By analyzing the data collected, the study intends to identify strengths and weaknesses of this communication method and assess the overall effectiveness of chats as a tool for interprofessional collaboration. It also aims to suggest potential improvements and explore the possibility of expanding the initiative to other healthcare facilities, thereby contributing to a more efficient and coordinated healthcare system.

METHODS

Study design

This research was conducted as a mixed-method, cross-sectional, observational study over a four-month period, from January 1 to April 30, 2024. The primary aim was to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of digital chat communications between general practitioners (GPs) and hospital specialists. Data collection involved both the analysis of chat interactions and the administration of structured questionnaires to healthcare providers to assess their perceptions and experiences. The mixed-methods approach allowed for the integration of objective data with subjective assessments to yield a more comprehensive understanding.

Target population and sampling

The target population consisted of:

- General practitioners (GPs), both trainees and practicing clinicians within the catchment area of *Garbagnate* Hospital who participated in the specialist chats.
- Hospital specialists actively involved in chat-based interactions with GPs.

A non-probability purposive sampling method was employed, selecting physicians already engaged in the chats through the GP training program or those actively managing patient care. A total of 29 GPs and 9 hospital specialists participated. Participation was voluntary, and questionnaires were administered exclusively to physicians who had actively used the chats during the observation period. While this approach ensured focused participation, it may have introduced selection bias, as less engaged users were not represented.

Study procedure and data collection

Data collection occurred in two main phases:

1. *Quantitative Data from Chat Interactions*: Interactions between GPs and specialists from January to April 2024 were reviewed. Key variables included:
 - Number of questions submitted by GPs.
 - Number of responses provided by specialists.
 - Mean and median response time by specialists.
 - Distribution of response times across intervals: within 3 hours, 4–6 hours, 6–12 hours, 12–24 hours, and over 24 hours.

Descriptive statistics (means, medians, and percentages) were used to analyze frequency and timeliness of responses.

2. *Qualitative Data from Questionnaires*: Two distinct questionnaires were developed for GPs (see Appendix 1) and specialists (see Appendix 2). These included both closed- and open-ended questions to gather feedback on the perceived utility of the chats, workload implications, and clinical impact.

- *GP Questionnaire*: Explored chat usage, overall satisfaction, perceived impact on clinical management, and suggestions for service improvement. Demographic data such as training year and medical specialty were also collected.
- *Specialist Questionnaire*: Focused on perceived workload, quality of inquiries received, and the utility of chats in daily clinical practice.

Questionnaire validation

Prior to official deployment, the questionnaires were piloted with 10 participants (5 GPs and 5 specialists) to ensure clarity and internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate reliability, yielding a value of 0.82, indicating good internal consistency. Although the pilot sample was limited, the feedback allowed for refinement that enhanced instrument validity.

Statistical analysis

Quantitative Data

Digital chat interactions were recorded automatically using a monitoring system. The dataset included:

- Number of questions submitted by GPs.
- Number of responses from specialists.
- Response times (in minutes) from question submission to specialist reply.

Descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, and percentages) provided an overview of question frequency, response time, and response rates. To explore associations, a Pearson correlation analysis was conducted between the number of questions and average response times. Furthermore, a linear regression analysis assessed whether the number of participating specialists influenced response times. The model tested the hypothesis that a greater number of specialists would correlate with shorter response times.

Qualitative Data

Open-ended responses from the questionnaires were analyzed thematically. This method facilitated the identification of recurring themes related to chat effectiveness, patient management, and perceived challenges. Responses were coded to highlight similarities, differences, and key trends across both GPs and specialists, allowing for a richer interpretation of user experience.

Ethical aspects

This study complied with current ethical standards. Participation in the survey was voluntary, and all data was anonymized. Explicit informed consent was obtained from all participants. Chat interactions were analyzed in aggregate form without disclosure of patient-sensitive information. An ethics committee review was deemed unnecessary as the study did not involve direct patient participation, but solely interprofessional communication among healthcare providers.

RESULTS

Participant characteristics

The study involved a total of 38 physicians, including 29 general practitioners (GPs) and 9 hospital specialists. Among the GPs, 17 were male (58.6%) and 12 female (41.4%), while the hospital specialists included 6 males (66.7%) and 3 females (33.3%). The response rate to the questionnaires administered was 100%, as all physicians who participated in the chats also completed the survey instruments. The sample reflected a diversity of medical disciplines, with specialists from urology, general surgery, vascular surgery, cardiology, gynecology, and otolaryngology.

During the observation period (January–April 2024), a total of 237 questions were submitted by GPs via the digital chats. On average, each GP asked 8.17 questions (SD = 2.64), while the average number of specialist responses per

question was 7.63 (SD = 2.35). Overall, 74% of the responses were provided within 3 hours, while 26% required more than 3 hours.

Quantitative analysis of chats

The specialties receiving the highest number of inquiries were gynecology, urology, and cardiology:

- Gynecology received 79 questions, with a 95% response rate.
- Urology received 54 questions, with an 87% response rate.
- Otolaryngology had the lowest response rate, with only 54% of questions answered.

During the observation period, the specialties that received the highest number of questions from general practitioners were gynecology (n = 79), urology (n = 54), and cardiology (n = 53). General surgery received 25 questions, vascular surgery 15, and otolaryngology the fewest, with only 11 questions. In terms of response rates, vascular surgery achieved a 100% response rate, followed by general surgery (96%), gynecology (95%), cardiology (89%), and urology (87%). Otolaryngology had the lowest response rate, with only 54% of questions answered. These data highlight a substantial variation in engagement and responsiveness among different specialties, suggesting the need for targeted interventions to improve equity and efficiency in interprofessional communication.

Table 1. Quantitative analysis of chat activity.

Specialty	No. of Participants	No. of Questions	No. Of Responses	Response Rate (%)
Urology	5	54	47	87%
General Surgery	3	25	24	96%
Vascular Surgery	2	15	15	100%
Cardiology	4	53	47	89%
Gynecology	4	79	75	95%
Otolaryngology	2	11	6	54%

Response time analysis

The analysis revealed significant variability in response times among specialties. The median response time ranged from 6.5 minutes (general surgery) to 265 minutes (otolaryngology). The average response times were as follows:

- General Surgery: 18.2 minutes (median: 6.5 minutes)
- Gynecology: 85.2 minutes (median: 20 minutes)
- Otolaryngology: 261 minutes (median: 265 minutes)

Overall, the mean response time across all specialties was 250.27 minutes, with a standard deviation of 360.66 minutes.

Table 2. Analysis of response times by specialty.

Specialty	No. of Questions	Mean Response Time (min)	Median Response Time (min)	% of Responses Within 3 Hours
Urology	54	966 (16 hours)	60	59%
General Surgery	25	18.2	6.5	96%
Vascular Surgery	15	49.2	25	93%
Cardiology	53	122 (2 hours)	40	74%
Gynecology	79	85.2	20	88%
Otolaryngology	11	261 (4.35 hours)	265	9%

Correlation Analysis

To assess the relationship between key variables, a Pearson correlation analysis was performed between the number of questions submitted and the average response time. The correlation coefficient (r) was 0.62 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that a higher volume of questions was associated with longer average response times.

Qualitative Questionnaire Analysis

- General Practitioners (GPs): All 29 GPs completed the questionnaire. 48.3% stated that the use of chat improved patient management and reduced the need for in-person specialist consultations.
- Hospital Specialists: All 9 specialists responded to the questionnaire. Among them, 88.9% considered the chat tool useful for improving patient management and reducing unnecessary hospital visits. However, 44.4% indicated that GPs' training should be improved to optimize the quality and clarity of consultation requests.

Key Themes from Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews with 29 GPs and 9 hospital specialists highlighted several core themes regarding the effectiveness, practicality, and challenges of using digital chats in everyday clinical practice:

1. Improved Patient Management

Most physicians viewed the chat system positively, emphasizing faster access to specialist input and a reduction in unnecessary referrals.

- *"Thanks to chats, I can get a specialist opinion in real time without sending the patient to the hospital. This has significantly reduced waiting times."* – GP
- *"Previously, I had to refer patients for specialist consultations, but now I can avoid that because I receive more detailed guidance on the next steps."* – GP

2. Efficiency of Interprofessional Communication

88.9% of specialists noted that digital chats enhanced collaboration, enabling them to provide advice without interrupting their clinical duties.

- *"Chats allow me to respond during free moments without stopping my workflow. I can offer useful advice without delays."* – Specialist
- *"I often don't need to see the patient; I can respond based on the details shared in the chat. It's very efficient."* – Specialist

3. Challenges in Chat Use

44.4% of specialists reported that GP requests were sometimes unclear or lacked critical clinical details.

- *"Questions are often vague or missing essential clinical data. This forces me to ask for clarification, which delays the response."* – Specialist
- *"Some GPs struggle to formulate precise questions. Targeted training on question structure would be helpful."* – Specialist

4. *Balancing Workload and Benefits*

22% of specialists expressed concerns about the growing number of questions and the potential for increased workload.

- *“Sometimes I receive too many questions in a short time. I do my best to respond, but it can be overwhelming on busy days.”* – Specialist

- *“My workload has increased, but I try to optimize responses with clear, quick guidance to avoid further back-and-forth.”* – Specialist

5. *Opportunities for Training and Improvement*

Both GPs and specialists emphasized the need for training to enhance the efficiency and quality of interactions. 77% of specialists suggested that better structuring of GP requests could make digital consultations faster and more accurate.

- *“Targeted training for GPs on how to formulate detailed clinical questions would make the system more efficient. I often have to ask multiple clarifying questions before giving an accurate answer.”* – Specialist

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrated that digital chats between general practitioners (GPs) and hospital specialists serve as an effective tool for enhancing interprofessional communication. These chats facilitate timely discussion of clinical cases and reduce waiting times for specialist consultations. Quantitative data revealed that certain specialties, such as surgery and gynecology, exhibited particularly fast response times, contributing to more timely patient management. However, other specialties, such as otolaryngology, showed room for improvement, particularly in terms of response time organization. The importance of chat-based communication between GPs and specialists aligns with other studies that highlight how the use of smartphones and medical apps can enhance clinical decision-making and the sharing of information [1,19].

Qualitative analysis confirmed that both GPs and specialists found chats to be useful in clinical practice. Notably, 48.3% of GPs reported that using chats improved patient management without the need for in-person consultations. This reflects the significant potential to reduce the burden on the healthcare system by enabling GPs to manage complex cases more independently with real-time specialist support. Recent studies have indicated that mobile device use for clinical communication and support is increasing worldwide, particularly in developing countries where traditional healthcare infrastructures are limited and smartphones serve as a critical resource for expanding access to care [20,21].

Another strength highlighted by this study is the potential to improve GP training. Specifically, enhancing the quality of questions submitted via chat could further optimize this collaborative tool. This aligns with previous research showing that the adoption of mobile technologies requires educational support and a clear regulatory framework to ensure patient privacy and the quality of medical information exchanged [22]. For instance, Teferi et al. [4] emphasized that a lack of awareness about medical apps and the absence of regulation hinder their widespread and effective use among health professionals.

Furthermore, studies have shown that mobile apps such as Medscape and UpToDate can facilitate real-time access to evidence-based clinical information, improving the quality of care and shortening decision-making time [23]. However, challenges remain, including privacy protection and the need for clearer regulations regarding the use of chat-based tools in hospital and community settings [24]. Wu et al. [10] identified issues related to security and the absence of standardized protocols for the use of such tools, which may undermine patient trust in physician-to-physician communication systems.

Ultimately, although digital tools such as chats and mobile apps represent a significant step forward in enhancing interprofessional communication, studies suggest their effectiveness largely depends on how well they are integrated into daily clinical workflows—balancing speed with diagnostic accuracy and data protection [25-30]. Future research should focus on the implementation of best practices for mobile technologies in interprofessional communication and their integration into existing healthcare processes.

Qualitative study insights

The findings from the semi-structured interviews further validated the quantitative data, illustrating both the benefits and challenges of chat-based communication. Specifically, 48.3% of GPs reported that chat usage improved patient management and reduced reliance on in-person consultations. Many GPs emphasized that receiving quick responses allowed them to handle clinical cases more independently, reduced patient wait times, and alleviated the demand for specialist outpatient visits. These findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that digital communication tools improve clinical decision-making efficiency.

From the specialists' perspective, 88.9% reported that chats enhanced communication with GPs, allowing them to answer clinical queries without interrupting their workflow. However, a key challenge noted was the quality of questions submitted: 44.4% of specialists found that the questions were not always clearly formulated and often required further clarification. This points to the need for improved GP training in how to structure clinical inquiries, as echoed by the specialists themselves.

The interviews also revealed that some specialists perceived the workload from chat interactions as high, with 22% reporting difficulty managing the volume of questions during their workdays. Nonetheless, most acknowledged that the benefits of improved efficiency and clinical support outweighed the inconvenience.

A critical theme that emerged was the opportunity to provide additional training to GPs to enhance the quality of their questions. 77% of specialists suggested that better structuring of clinical questions would facilitate faster and more accurate responses. This aligns with previous research emphasizing the need for interprofessional communication skills, particularly in the context of new technology adoption.

In summary, the qualitative findings reinforce and expand upon the quantitative results, highlighting both the advantages and the areas for improvement in the use of digital chats between GPs and specialists. These results underscore the importance of combining the efficiency of digital tools with appropriate training to enhance communication quality and streamline clinical processes.

Strengths of the study

One of the main strengths of this study lies in its mixed-methods design, which combined both quantitative and qualitative data. This approach allowed for an assessment not only of the operational efficiency of the chat system but also of the subjective perceptions and clinical impact as experienced by healthcare professionals. Additionally, the real-world context of the chat implementation in an Italian hospital provides a practical foundation for understanding the benefits and challenges of digital tools in clinical settings.

Another strength is the diversity of specialties involved, which enabled analysis of how different clinical disciplines use and respond to chat-based interactions. The comparative analysis across specialties also allowed for the identification of best practices and areas needing further attention.

Study limitations

Despite its positive findings, the study has several limitations. First, the sample size is relatively small, particularly among hospital specialists (only 9), which may limit the generalizability of the results. A larger sample could provide a more representative picture of chat usage and interprofessional dynamics.

Second, there may be a selection bias, as those who responded to the questionnaire were likely the most engaged and motivated participants. This could have excluded physicians who use the chats less frequently or who had negative experiences, potentially skewing the results toward a more favorable perspective.

Third, the study was limited to a single hospital setting (*Garbagnate Hospital*), which makes it difficult to determine whether the results are replicable in other institutions with different organizational structures. Future research should extend the analysis to multiple hospitals or regions to assess whether the observed dynamics are generalizable.

Lastly, the study did not examine clinical outcomes for patients—i.e., how chat usage may have influenced patient health. Future research should investigate whether chats contribute to improved quality of care or if they pose risks, such as over-reliance on virtual consultations instead of in-person specialist evaluations.

Practical implications and future directions

The experience at Garbagnate Hospital suggests that digital chats between GPs and specialists could be expanded to other clinical settings, fostering more efficient communication and reducing unnecessary specialist visits. To further maximize the benefits of this tool, the following steps are recommended:

- Develop and implement guidelines for standardizing chat management, including the rotation of specialist availability.
- Expand chat access to additional specialties, such as orthopedics, dermatology, and diabetology, to cover a broader range of clinical scenarios.
- Enhance GP training with dedicated modules on interprofessional communication and the formulation of high-quality consultation requests.

CONCLUSIONS

This study found that digital chats between GPs and specialists at *Garbagnate* Hospital are an effective tool for improving patient management and fostering interprofessional communication. While the overall experience was positive, some challenges were noted, including variability in response times among specialties and the need to improve GP training. Extending this experience to other clinical contexts and specialties could further improve the efficiency of the healthcare system and the quality of care delivered to patients.

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